

First-Year Non-English Majored Students' Perspectives on the use of Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning at Thai Nguyen University of Technology

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a study on investigating first-year non-English majored students on the use of digital technology at Thai Nguyen University of Technology. This study employed a quantitative research approach. Data was collected through a survey with a structured questionnaire. The findings reveal that students recognize the importance of using digital technology in vocabulary learning, as it allows them to study conveniently anytime and anywhere. In addition, digital technology is effective in increasing students' motivation and engagement. However, they are less convinced of its effectiveness in facilitating vocabulary acquisition and improving understanding. Therefore, educators should guide students in effective digital learning strategies and in selecting appropriate tools.

KEYWORDS: digital technology, vocabulary learning, motivation, effectiveness, types

I. INTRODUCTION

In the process of learning English as a foreign language (EFL), vocabulary learning plays an important role in developing students' communication and language skills. In recent years, digital technology has advanced rapidly. This rapid development has had a positive impact on many fields, including English language teaching and learning. It has changed the way students learn vocabulary through new tools and platforms such as mobile learning apps and social media platforms.

In the Vietnamese EFL context, even though digital tools are widely popular and accessible, there is limited research on how university students perceive the use of digital technology in English vocabulary learning. This study aims to investigate non-English major students' perceptions, frequency of use, and preferred digital tools for vocabulary learning in English.

The findings of the study are expected to provide useful implications for teachers on how to effectively use digital tools to enhance vocabulary learning.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Vocabulary Learning

Different scholars have given different definitions of vocabulary. According to Penny Ur (1996), vocabulary refers to the words taught in a foreign language. Nation shares a similar view with Ur but provides a more comprehensive explanation by stating that "knowing a word involves knowing its form, meaning, and use" (Nation, 2001, p. 27).

Vocabulary plays a very important role in learning English. As Wilkins indicated, "Without grammar, very little can be conveyed but without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed" (Wilkins, 1972, as cited in Thornbury, 2002, p. 13). This statement emphasizes the importance of vocabulary in communication because, although grammar is essential, learners cannot express their ideas without sufficient vocabulary.

However, learning vocabulary in a foreign language is a complex and challenging process (Schmitt, 2008; Laufer 2017). Schmitt (2008) presents that learners need to acquire a large vocabulary size and develop deep knowledge of words through repeated exposure and use. In other words, learning vocabulary includes not only understanding word meanings but also knowing their pronunciation, grammatical functions, spelling, collocations, and suitable use in different contexts. Therefore, vocabulary learning requires continuous practice and repeated encounters with words over time in order to achieve effective language use.

Therefore, many educators have attempted to integrate technology into vocabulary teaching and learning to make it more effective and motivating.

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2. Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning

With the development of technology in today's world, it has a great influence on learning methods and offers numerous undeniable benefits (Reinders et al., 2022). The authors also indicate that "digital technology can be any tool that involves the use of computing power, such as a calculator, a mobile phone, or an autonomous vehicle" (Reinders et al., 2022, p.7).

Digital technology has become increasingly important in vocabulary learning. Many scholars have studied the effects of digital technology on vocabulary learning. Digital technology-based learning motivated students and made their vocabulary learning more effective (Hazar, 2020; Tebeweka, 2021; Metruk & Zimenová, 2025).

Nevertheless, besides the benefits, digital technology brings several disadvantages. Students would face distraction and reliance on constant internet access (Babazade, 2024). Overall, digital technology is a useful tool that can increase students' motivation and engagement. Therefore, investigating students' perspectives on the use of digital technology is necessary to better understand students' needs.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. Research Questions

This study aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What are first-year non-English majored students' perspectives on the use of digital technology in vocabulary learning?
2. What suggestions can be given to enhance students' vocabulary learning?

2. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research approach using survey design. This method was chosen because the study aimed to measure and analyze first-year non-English majored students' perspectives and attitudes towards the use of digital technology in vocabulary learning. The quantitative approach allowed the collection of data from a relatively large number of participants and facilitated statistical analysis.

3. Research Context and Participants

The study was conducted at Thai Nguyen University of Technology. The participants were 54 first-year students majoring in Electrical Engineering. Convenience sampling was used to select the participants from a single class.

4. Research Instruments

The data of the study were collected through a survey which consisted of a structured questionnaire, adapted from Klimova & Plakova (2020). The questionnaire included 13 questions, eight of which were five-point Likert-scale questions (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The questionnaire was written in Vietnamese to avoid possible misunderstanding and divided into four parts. The first part was designed to collect participants' demographic information, consisting of their genders, the year of English learning and English learning experience. The second part aimed to seek information on what types of digital technology they used. The third part was to examine the frequency of using different types of technology. The fourth part was used to investigate teachers' perceptions of digital technology use in vocabulary learning

5. Data Collection Procedures

The questionnaire was distributed in paper form to the 54 participating students by the researcher and collected on the same day. The collected data was analyzed through the descriptive statistical procedures of SPSS Version 20.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the study, followed by the corresponding data analysis.

1. Types of Digital Technology Used in Vocabulary Learning

It is indicated from Table 1 that AI tools were the most frequently used (79.6%), followed by social media platforms (75.9%) and online video platforms (66.7%). In contrast, specialized vocabulary learning tools such as mobile applications and game-based platforms were used by considerably fewer participants.

Table 1 Types of Digital Technology Used in Vocabulary Learning

	Digital tools	Frequency	Percentage of Cases (%)
1	AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini)	43	79.6%
2	Social media platforms (e.g., TikTok, Facebook)	41	75.9%
3	Online video platforms (e.g., YouTube)	36	66.7%
4	Online dictionaries (e.g., Cambridge, Oxford)	19	35.2%
5	Mobile learning applications (e.g.,	18	33.3%

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	Quizlet, Duolingo, Memrise)		
6	Game-based learning tools (e.g., Kahoot, Wordwall, Blooket)	7	13.0%
	Others	0	0%
Total responses		164	

The findings suggest that students prefer using easy and interactive digital platforms rather than language learning applications. The frequent use of AI tools suggests that students like quick and flexible support for vocabulary learning. In addition, the popularity of social media and YouTube shows that students enjoy interesting and real-life content that is closely connected to their daily lives.

2. Frequency of Using Different Types of Technology

As can be seen from table 2 that digital technology has become a regular part of vocabulary learning for most participants, although most respondents still used it at moderate level. While nearly 60% of students used digital tools “Sometimes”, over one-third used them “Often” or “Very often”. This suggests that digital technology is now well-integrated into students’ study routines.

Table 2. Frequency of using digital technology to learn vocabulary

	Frequency	Percent (%)
rarely	3	5.5
sometimes	32	59.3
often	11	20.4
very often	8	14.8
Total	54	100.0

The moderate use of digital technology in vocabulary learning suggests that students no longer rely on the traditional materials such as textbooks. However, a small percentage of students rarely use digital technology in learning, which is uncommon among students.

3. Students' Motivation in Vocabulary Learning Through Digital Technology

As shown in Table 3, students expressed a very high level of motivation when using digital tools. The majority of students (M=4.57, SD = 0.79) agreed that they felt more motivated to learn vocabulary when using digital tools. Similarly, students reported that using digital technology made vocabulary learning more enjoyable and less stressful, with a mean score of 4.54 (SD = 0.82).

Table 3. Students' Motivation When Using Digital Technology

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel more motivated to learn vocabulary when using digital tools	54	2.00	5.00	4.5741	.79151
Using digital technology makes vocabulary learning more enjoyable and less stressful	54	2.00	5.00	4.5370	.81757
Valid N	54				

The findings reveal that students perceive digital technology as an effective tool for enhancing motivation in vocabulary learning. This aligns with previous research (Hazar, 2020; Tebeweka, 2021; Metruk & Zimenová, 2025) indicating that digital technology-based learning can increase students’ engagement and reduce anxiety.

4. Perceived Convenience and Autonomy of Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning

It can be seen from table 4 that students showed strong agreement related to the convenience offered by digital technology in vocabulary learning. A large number of respondents agreed that using digital technology was convenient because they could learn vocabulary anytime and anywhere, with a mean score of 4.39 (SD = 1.05).

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Additionally, students also expressed positive perceptions toward the role of digital technology in supporting independent learning. The statement "Digital technology helps me learn vocabulary independently" received a mean score of 4.20 (SD = 0.81).

Table 4. Perceived Convenience and Autonomy of Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Using digital technology is convenient because I can learn vocabulary anytime and anywhere	54	1.00	5.00	4.3889	1.05360
Digital technology helps me learn vocabulary independently	54	1.00	5.00	4.2037	.80984
Valid N	54				

This finding highlights one of the greatest advantages of digital learning, which helps students to overcome constraints of time and location when learning English vocabulary. Additionally, the high level of agreement regarding the positive impact of digital technology on independent learning reflects the broader shift toward learner-centered education, where students can better control their own vocabulary learning through AI tools and other digital resources.

These findings are consistent with previous studies on technology use in vocabulary learning, which emphasizes that convenience and autonomy are among the factors contributing to students' motivation in vocabulary acquisition through the use of digital technology.

5. The Effectiveness of Using Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning

Table 5 indicates that the highest mean score was found with the statement "Digital technology is an important tool in learning English vocabulary" (M = 3.8519, SD = 1.08866). In contrast, the two lowest mean scores appeared in the statements regarding understanding and ease of vocabulary acquisition: "Digital technology helps me understand new vocabulary better" (M = 2.8704) and "Digital technology makes vocabulary learning easier for me" (M = 2.9074). The perception of improvement in overall vocabulary learning performance was slightly above neutral (M = 3.1667).

Overall, participants showed moderately positive attitudes toward digital technology in vocabulary learning. However, there is a clear gap between students' recognition of the importance of digital tools and their actual learning experiences in terms of ease of learning and improved understanding.

Table 5. The Effectiveness of Using Digital Technology in Vocabulary Learning

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Digital technology makes vocabulary learning easier for me	54	1.00	5.00	2.9074	1.36352
Digital technology helps me understand new vocabulary better	54	1.00	5.00	2.8704	1.31818
Digital technology improves my overall vocabulary learning performances	54	1.00	5.00	3.1667	1.42418
Digital technology is an important tool in learning English vocabulary	54	1.00	5.00	3.8519	1.08866
Valid N	54				

The findings show that although students perceive digital technology as an important tool for vocabulary learning (M = 3.85), they were not fully convinced about its actual effectiveness in making learning easier (M = 2.91) or helping them understand new words better (M = 2.87). This suggests that though learners are aware of the technology's potential, they may not fully benefit from it in practice.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The study examines first-year non-English majored students' perspective on technology use of digital technology in English vocabulary learning. The findings provide better understanding of how university students integrate digital tools into their learning process. The results show an enhancement in students' motivation, independent vocabulary learning, and the ability to learn

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vocabulary anytime and anywhere. However, there exists a gap report that digital training is not particularly effective in making their learning easier or improving their understanding. This suggests that the advantages of digital tools depend on how students use the tools rather than whether or frequently they use them.

Therefore, teachers and educators should guide students on how to use the digital technology effectively and integrate it into teaching to enhance student engagement in learning.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to thank Thai Nguyen University of Technology for its support and for providing the academic environment that made this study possible.

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